

Dual GLP-1/GIP agonist tirzepatide modulates hepatic mitochondrial fusion–fission gene expression and oxidative stress in diabetic rats

Shams Dhiaa Fakhir¹, Inam Sameh Arif¹, Huda Jaber Waheed¹

¹ Pharmacology and Toxicology Department, College of Pharmacy, Mustansiriyah University, Baghdad, Iraq

Corresponding author: Shams Dhiaa Fakhir (shams_dhiaa96@uomustansiriyah.edu.iq)

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Abstract

Type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) is closely linked to oxidative stress–induced mitochondrial dysfunction, disrupting the balance between fusion and fission processes and driving hepatic injury. Tirzepatide (TZP), a dual GLP-1/GIP receptor agonist, is recognized for its potent glycemic and weight-lowering effects, yet its influence on hepatic mitochondrial dynamics in diabetes remains unclear. In this study, diabetes was induced in Wistar rats using a high-fat diet and streptozotocin, followed by treatment with varying doses of TZP. Diabetic animals exhibited marked hyperglycemia, insulin resistance, elevated lipid peroxidation, reduced antioxidant capacity, and altered expression of mitochondrial fusion and fission markers, accompanied by significant hepatic inflammation and degeneration. TZP administration improved glycemic indices, restored redox balance, enhanced the expression of fusion-related genes (Mfn1, Mfn2, Opa1), and suppressed the expression of fission-related genes (Drp1, Fis1) in a dose-dependent manner. Medium and high doses notably preserved liver histoarchitecture and reduced inflammatory changes. These findings suggest that TZP mitigates T2DM-associated hepatic injury by favoring mitochondrial fusion, alleviating oxidative stress, and protecting tissue integrity. The results provide mechanistic insights into TZP's hepatoprotective potential and highlight the need for further validation at protein and functional levels.

Keywords

liver, mitochondria, mitochondrial dynamics, oxidative stress, tirzepatide

Introduction

Diabetes mellitus (DM) is a multifactorial chronic disease and a collection of metabolic disorders distinguished by elevated blood glucose levels (hyperglycemia) (Hamid et al. 2018; Jawad et al. 2025). It is ranked as one of the most widespread long-term diseases worldwide. Researchers anticipate the global prevalence of diabetes mellitus will reach 643 million by 2030 and 783 million by 2045 (Chou et al. 2023). It is characterized by a defective or inadequate

insulin secretion response, which results in impaired glucose utilization and episodes of excessively high blood glucose levels (Numan et al. 2024). There are two major types of diabetes: type 1 diabetes, characterized by insulin deficiency and immune-mediated demise of pancreatic beta cells (Chiang et al. 2018). The predominant type of diabetes is type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) (Xu et al. 2018). It is a metabolic disease characterized by an imbalance in energy intake, leading to metabolic stress, an inflammatory stimulus, and elevated levels of fatty acids, triglycerides,

and LDL cholesterol (Lu et al. 2024). T2DM is associated with insulin resistance and is accompanied by varying degrees of β -cell dysfunction. It often coexists with other metabolic disorders, such as obesity (Atia et al. 2024).

The liver is a key organ that both influences and is affected by diabetes and hyperglycemia. T2DM is characterized by an increased rate of hepatic glucose production, resulting in fasting hyperglycemia (Gastaldelli et al. 2007). Increasing endogenous production of glucose can be attributed to an augmented activity of hepatic enzymes found in primary rat hepatocytes under high glucose stress (Sargsyan and Herman 2019). Moreover, a reduction in the production and activity of antioxidant enzymes was noted in primary rat hepatocytes subjected to high glucose levels (Kapoor and Kakkar 2012).

Mitochondria play a crucial role in maintaining cellular homeostasis by contributing to energy metabolism, biosynthetic processes, calcium signaling pathways, redox regulation, and the production of reactive oxygen species (ROS) (Fadhil et al. 2024). Mitochondria effectively generate cellular ATP and regulate ATP availability inside the cell, as they serve as the principal site for ATP synthesis (Boyman et al. 2020). The mitochondria exhibit a high level of structural flexibility, regulated by dynamic processes that continually alter their shape and number through the opposing actions of fission and fusion. These cellular processes help maintain mitochondrial shape and network dynamics (Gao and Hu 2021). Mitochondrial fusion involves the joining of two separate mitochondria to form a single, enlarged organelle (Green et al. 2022). Mitochondrial fission refers to the process whereby a single mitochondrion divides to form two separate daughter mitochondria (Green et al. 2022). Mitochondrial fusion involves the merging of both the outer mitochondrial membrane (OMM) and inner mitochondrial membrane (IMM). The process of OMM fusion is controlled by mitofusins, specifically Mfn1 and Mfn2, whereas IMM fusion is managed by Opa1 (optic atrophy 1) (Al Ojaimi et al. 2022). In contrast, fission is regulated by the recruitment of dynamin-related protein 1 (DRP1) through adaptor proteins, including fission 1 (FIS1), mitochondrial fission factor (MFF), and mitochondrial dynamics proteins of 49 and 51 kDa (MiD49 and MiD51) (Zerihun et al. 2023). Mitochondrial fusion is considered crucial for mitochondrial biogenesis, as it facilitates the exchange of mitochondrial DNA to preserve mitochondrial genomes and eliminate toxic compounds within mitochondria (Pernas and Scorrano 2016). At the same time, mitochondrial fission serves as a vital mechanism for the elimination of damaged mitochondria through mitophagy (Ni et al. 2015).

Modulations in mitochondrial dynamics occur across a wide range of physiological and pathological contexts, leading to morphological alterations of mitochondria that are essential for meeting cellular bioenergetic demands and mediating stress responses (Eisner et al. 2018). Any disruption in this balance can result in mitochondrial dysfunction, oxidative stress, and metabolic disorders, ultimately leading to mitochondrial-associated diseases

such as insulin resistance and T2DM (Bhatti et al. 2017). In T2DM, the mitochondrial fusion process diminishes while the fission process increases (Shan et al. 2022). Numerous studies have highlighted the physiological significance of mitochondrial dynamics and mitochondrial quality control, as well as the potential impact of disruptions in these processes on the pathogenesis of T2DM, obesity, and cardiovascular disease (Wai and Langer 2016). Hyperglycemia and T2DM are directly associated with oxidative stress, and hyperglycemia induces mitochondrial fragmentation in various cell types, including those in the liver, pancreas, and cardiovascular system (Rovira-Llopis et al. 2017). All these factors suggest that mitochondria play a significant role in the pathogenesis of DM and contribute substantially to the exacerbation of liver injury. It will be essential for studying the relationship between changes in mitochondrial dynamics and T2DM-induced hepatic mitochondrial dysfunction (Pinti et al. 2019).

Recent years have seen a significant increase in research focused on interventions and techniques aimed at modulating mitochondrial fusion and fission processes. Tirzepatide (TZP), a dual agonist of glucose-dependent insulinotropic peptide (GIP) and glucagon-like peptide-1 (GLP-1) receptors, has recently been approved for the management of T2DM and obesity (Alshehri et al. 2025), exhibiting greater efficacy for glycemic management and weight loss in comparison to monospecific receptor agonists (El et al. 2023). This study examines the effects of TZP administration and its impact on the expression of fusion proteins Mfn1/2 and Opa1, as well as fission proteins Drp1 and mitochondrial Fis1, in special pathways that maintain mitochondrial dynamics in high-fat diet and STZ-induced diabetic rats. The mechanisms of action behind the involvement of TZP in hepatic mitochondrial dynamics in HFD/STZ-induced diabetic rats have not been investigated. As a result, an in-depth examination of the effect of TZP on hepatic mitochondrial dynamics is crucial to clarify its mechanism of action and provide a basis for formulating targeted therapy strategies to reestablish balance in the fission and fusion processes of mitochondrial dynamics related to T2DM.

Methods

Chemicals and reagents

Tirzepatide was provided by Macklin (Shanghai, China), and streptozotocin was purchased from Meryer (Shanghai, China). Sodium pentobarbital (Dolethal Solution for Injection, Vetoquinol UK Ltd, United Kingdom). TRIzol reagent and tissue lysis reagent were purchased from TransGen Biotech, China. The RNA extraction and cDNA synthesis kit was also purchased from TransGen Biotech, China. Primers for Mfn2, Opa1, Fis1, Drp1, and glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate dehydrogenase (GAPDH) were ordered from Macrogen, South Korea. Rat ELISA kits for GSH (Cat. # MBS265966), insulin (Cat. # ELK10406), and

MDA (Cat. # ELK10920) were purchased from ELK Biotechnology and MyBioSource.

Experimental animals

Thirty male Wistar rats, aged 6–7 weeks and weighing between 100 and 120 grams, were included in the experiment, with six animals per group. The rats were housed four per cage and allowed to acclimate for one week in a controlled environment with temperatures ranging from 22 to 25 °C, humidity levels of 40–50%, and a 12-h light/dark cycle. The study adhered to the animal care, handling, and euthanasia guidelines set by the AVMA 2020 (Karwi et al. 2018; Underwood and Anthony 2020). All experiments were carried out under the guidelines of the Institutional Review Board of Mustansiriyah University's College of Pharmacy, Pharmacology, and Toxicology Department (Approval number: 87, Reference number: 190, Date: 8 October 2024). The methods used on the animals fully comply with regional and international regulations governing the ethical treatment and use of laboratory animals. The authors complied with the ARRIVE 2.0 guidelines (Percie du Sert et al. 2020).

Experimental protocol

Thirty male Wistar strain rats were randomly allocated into five groups. The control group consisted of rats that were fed a regular pellet and received an injection of citrate buffer at the same time as induction. They were then subcutaneously (SC) injected with deionized water throughout the experimental treatment and maintained under standard care without receiving any therapy by the end of the trial.

In the induction group, the rats received HFD for six weeks. At the end of the 6th week, the rats received a single intraperitoneal (IP) injection of STZ at 35 mg/kg (Binh et al. 2013). After one week, the success of diabetic induction was confirmed by a tail-vein blood sample using a One Touch glucometer and test strip from On Call Plus

(ACON Laboratories Inc., San Diego, CA 92121, USA). Rats exhibiting fasting blood glucose levels beyond 250 mg/dL at 72 h after STZ administration were included in the study (Abd-Alhussain et al. 2024).

Low-dose TZP group: rats received the induction as in the induction group. At the end of the 7th week, the rats received weekly SC doses of 0.44 mg/kg TZP for 4 weeks. Medium-dose TZP group: rats received the induction as in the induction group. At the end of the 7th week, the rats received weekly SC doses of 0.88 mg/kg TZP for 4 weeks. High-dose TZP group: rats received the induction as in the induction group. At the end of the 7th week, the rats received weekly SC doses of 1.32 mg/kg TZP for 4 weeks (Hegab et al. 2024), as illustrated in Fig. 1. The animal dose of TZP was determined by converting human doses (5, 10, and 15 mg for adults, assuming a 70 kg body weight) to animal doses (Nair and Jacob 2016), in addition to previous studies on rats (Hegab et al. 2024).

Induced diabetes

The diabetic model was developed based on previous studies (Binh et al. 2013). This can be accomplished by integrating HFD, which induces insulin resistance, hyperinsulinemia, and obesity but does not cause sustained hyperglycemia or diabetes. Thus, inducing diabetes requires administering a low dose of STZ, which results in initial β -cell malfunction. The standard pellet diet used in our animal housing facilities consists of 2% fat, 57% carbohydrates, 17.5% protein, 4.9% vitamin and mineral mix, 6.6% fiber, and 12% water, yielding a total caloric content of approximately 3160 kcal/kg (percentage by weight). The HFD consisted of 60% of calories from fat (animal fat), 26.2% from carbohydrates, and 13.8% from protein, with a total caloric content of around 5200 kcal/kg. Following six weeks of dietary modifications, a single low dose of STZ (35 mg/kg) administered intraperitoneally resulted in elevated blood glucose levels within 3 days post-injection. Before injection, the rats underwent overnight fasting, while they were allowed to drink their

Figure 1. Flow chart of the study.

usual water. On the same day, a fresh STZ solution was prepared by dissolving STZ in citrate buffer (pH 4.5) 5 minutes before the planned injection. On the same day as the STZ injection, we replaced the water with 10% sucrose water to prevent hypoglycemia that can occur after STZ injection. On the second day after STZ injection, we replaced the 10% sucrose water with regular water. The rats in the control group received a vehicle consisting of citrate buffer (pH 4.5). To verify diabetes, we selected rats exhibiting fasting blood glucose levels above 250 mg/dL 72 h post-administration of STZ. Following this, we allowed all the rats to continue their respective diets and closely monitored them until the study's conclusion to ensure the stability of the diabetic model (Binh et al. 2013; Abd-Alhussain et al. 2024).

Animal care

This study adheres to the AVMA 2020 Guidelines for the Care and Use of Laboratory Animals. Every effort was made to minimize animal suffering and distress. All procedures were performed in accordance with the principles of refinement, reduction, and replacement. Animals were closely monitored immediately after STZ injection and continued to be observed over subsequent days. During blood glucose monitoring, any bleeding was promptly controlled, and the injection site was disinfected with sterile gauze and water. In cases of signs of infection, a veterinarian was consulted to assess the animal's health and suitability for continued participation in the experiment.

Measurement of body weight

During the 11-week study period, the body weight of each animal was carefully measured and recorded on a weekly basis. These measurements were taken using a precise animal balance to ensure accuracy and consistency across all data points. This systematic approach allowed for detailed tracking of weight changes over time, providing valuable data for analyzing the effects observed during the study.

Sample collection

At the end of the study's duration (the end of the 11th week), rats were anesthetized with IP anesthesia using pentobarbital 200 mg/kg before euthanasia by exsanguination (Pang and Laferriere 2020). Blood specimens were obtained from the animals. After blood collection, the sample was centrifuged at 5000 rpm for 10 minutes to isolate the serum. The serum was collected in 2 ml Eppendorf tubes and stored at -20°C until the day of assessment. Following the animal euthanasia, the liver was excised, rinsed with ice-cold saline, and sectioned into two pieces. The first liver specimen was preserved in neutral buffered formalin (10%) and prepared for histological examination. The second liver specimen was placed in Eppendorf tubes with 1 mL of Triazole reagent and frozen at -40°C for RT-PCR analysis (Hammadi et al. 2025).

Assessment of biochemical analysis

Serum levels of insulin, glutathione (GSH), and malondialdehyde (MDA) were determined using the enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA), which utilizes a sandwich enzyme immunoassay approach. Insulin resistance was estimated through the homeostasis model assessment of insulin resistance (HOMA-IR), calculated by multiplying fasting plasma glucose (mg/dL) by fasting plasma insulin (mIU/L) and dividing the product by 405 (Hammadi et al. 2025; Kadhim et al. 2025).

We quantified serum levels of MDA and GSH to assess systemic oxidative stress concurrently with hepatic gene expression analysis and histological examination. We recognize that tissue-specific assays on liver samples would yield more precise information on hepatic redox status.

Measurement of gene expression levels using real-time PCR

Real-time PCR was performed for five specific genes: Mfn1 (F: TGATCTCAATTGCCACAAGC, R: ATAGGCTCTGACAGCCCAAG), Mfn2 (F: CTGGTCCCTCGACAGTGTTT, R: ATCATTGTAGCCAGCAAGG), Opa1 (F: TGCCCTCAAGCTTCAAAGAC, R: GAGCCTTG-CAGCTAACCTTG), Drp1 (F: CAGAGACTGTTTAC-CAGACTGA, R: TGTACTTTGCCGTTCCCTTCA), and Fis1 (F: TGAAAGGAAATTTTCAGTCTGAGC, R: AC-GATGCCTCTACGGATGTC). Total RNA was isolated from frozen liver tissues using the TransZol Up Plus RNA Kit (TransGen Biotech, China) according to the manufacturer's guidelines. The RNA sample concentrations were measured with a Nanodrop 2000 spectrophotometer. The extracted RNA was further transcribed to cDNA via reverse transcriptase using EasyScript[®] One-Step gDNA Removal and cDNA Synthesis SuperMix (TransGen Biotech, China) following the manufacturer's instructions. Real-time PCR reactions were performed using SYBR Green Supermix to measure mRNA expression levels (TransGen Biotech, China). The relative amount of gene expression was determined using the $2^{-\Delta\Delta\text{CT}}$ method, with GAPDH (F: AGAACATCATCCCTGCATCC, R: CAACG-GATACATTGGGGTA) serving as the validated internal control reference gene (Livak and Schmittgen 2001). Primer design was performed using Primer 2 software, and the primer sequences supplied by Macrogen, South Korea, were utilized.

Histopathological examination

The liver tissues were preserved in 10% neutral formalin overnight. The tissues underwent dehydration in ethanol with increasing concentrations, clarification in xylol, and embedding in paraffin blocks following standard procedures. Four-micrometer-thick liver sections were prepared using a microtome. The sections were washed in a water bath, mounted on glass slides, and placed in an oven to melt the wax. The slides were rehydrated and

stained with hematoxylin and eosin (H&E) (Obead et al. 2025). A light microscope was used to examine the H&E-stained tissue sections for histological changes. Liver cell lobular inflammation scores were assigned as follows: 0, indicating no inflammatory cells; 1, indicating 1–2 cells; 2, indicating 2–3 cells; and 3, indicating four or more cells. Additionally, five fields were randomly chosen at a magnification of $\times 40$ to assess inflammation in the portal area, with evaluations categorized as none, mild, moderate, or severe (Chen et al. 2016). Two independent histopathologists performed the evaluations, and they were blinded to the experimental groups.

Statistical analysis and sample size calculations

The “resource equation method” was used to calculate the sample size, assuming that we have four animals per block (randomized block design) and five treatment groups. To achieve the maximum design, six animals per group were required. The error in the degree of freedom was 20, which is within the acceptable range of 10–20; thus, a to-

tal sample size of 30 was the final sample size (Panos and Boeckler 2023). Statistical analyses were performed using GraphPad Prism 10.5. Experimental data are presented as mean \pm standard error. One-way analysis of variance was used to compare parametric data among groups, followed by a Tukey multiple comparisons *post hoc* test. The level of significance was <0.05 .

Results

Effect of TZP on glycemic control parameters and body weight

Induction with STZ resulted in a significant increase in FPG and HOMA-IR (insulin resistance) compared to the control group, as shown in Fig. 2A, C. Concurrently, fasting serum insulin levels were significantly reduced in the induction group relative to the control group (Fig. 2B). Treatment with TZP mitigated the diabetic condition induced by STZ, with all doses producing a significant reduction in serum FPG (Fig. 2A), HOMA-IR (Fig. 2C), and

Figure 2. Effect of tirzepatide on fasting plasma glucose, fasting insulin, HOMA-IR, and body weight. Data are presented as mean \pm SEM. Tirzepatide reduced hyperglycemia and insulin resistance while partially restoring insulin secretion, consistent with its known incretin-based mechanism of action. A) Effect on fasting plasma glucose, B) Effect on fasting insulin, C) Effect on HOMA-IR, D) Effect on body weight. Data are presented as mean \pm SEM (one-way ANOVA with *post hoc* Tukey test used for pairwise comparisons). * indicates p-value <0.05 ; **** indicate p-value <0.0001 ; and ns indicates no significant difference.

body weight (Fig. 2D) compared to the induction group, alongside a significant increase in serum insulin (Fig. 2B). Of note, we did not evaluate clamp-derived insulin sensitivity or β -cell mass.

Effect of TZP on oxidative stress biomarkers

Induction with STZ caused a significant increase in serum MDA levels and a decrease in GSH levels compared to the normal control group, as shown in Fig. 3A, B. All doses of TZP resulted in a significant reduction in MDA levels compared to the induction group. Moreover, a notable difference was observed between each dose, with higher doses producing a more pronounced decrease in MDA levels, indicating a dose-response relationship between higher doses and greater effects on MDA levels, as shown in Fig. 3A. Both medium-dose and high-dose TZP significantly increased GSH levels compared to the induction group; however, low-dose TZP caused a non-significant increase in GSH levels. Additionally, no significant differences were observed among the different TZP doses, as illustrated in Fig. 3B.

The effect of TZP on mitochondrial fusion protein gene expression

The gene expression levels of Mfn1, Mfn2, and Opa1 in control and diabetic rats (Fig. 4A–C) were affected by STZ- and HFD-induced diabetes. One-way ANOVA showed a significant decrease in Mfn1 expression in the

induction group compared to controls (0.312 vs. 1.32; $p < 0.001$). Treatment with TZP increased Mfn1 levels in a dose-dependent manner: low dose (1.2-fold), medium dose (1.92-fold), and high dose (5.64-fold). These levels were significantly higher than those in the induction group, with the high dose also surpassing the medium and low doses ($p < 0.0001$). For Mfn2, expression was reduced in the induction group (0.502 vs. 1.02; $p < 0.01$). TZP treatment increased Mfn2 expression at medium and high doses, with the high dose (1.54-fold) significantly higher than the control and induction groups ($p < 0.0001$). Similarly, Opa1 expression decreased in the induction group (0.242 vs. 1.01; $p < 0.0001$) and increased with TZP, with the high dose (1.24-fold) significantly surpassing the induction, medium, and low doses ($p < 0.0001$). Overall, TZP mitigated the reductions in gene expression induced by diabetes, with higher doses showing greater effects.

The effect of TZP on mitochondrial fission protein gene expression

Fig. 4D, E report gene expression levels of Drp1 and Fis1 across five groups of control and diabetic rats. STZ- and HFD-induced diabetes increased Fis1 and Drp1 expression. One-way ANOVA revealed a significant Fis1 increase in the induction group (1.87-fold) versus controls (0.915-fold; $p < 0.0001$). TZP doses decreased Fis1: low (1.29-fold), medium (0.693-fold), and high (0.58-fold) compared to induction, with the high dose showing the greatest reduction ($p < 0.0001$). For Drp1, induction increased expression (2.24-fold vs. 1.03-fold in controls;

Figure 3. Effect of TZP on oxidative stress markers. A) Effect of TZP on MDA, B) Effect of TZP on GSH. Data are presented as mean \pm SEM (one-way ANOVA with *post hoc* Tukey test used for pairwise comparisons). * indicates p -value < 0.05 ; ** indicate p -value < 0.01 ; **** indicate p -value < 0.0001 ; and ns indicates no significant difference.

Figure 4. Gene expression levels of mitochondrial fusion markers (Mfn1, Mfn2, Opa1) and fission markers (Fis1, Drp1). Tirzepatide dose-dependently enhanced fusion-related gene expression while suppressing fission-related gene expression, suggesting a mechanistic shift toward mitochondrial integrity and reduced fragmentation. A) Effect on Murefn1 gene expression, B) Effect on Mfn2 gene expression, C) Effect on Opa1 gene expression, D) Effect on Fis1 gene expression, E) Effect on Drp1 gene expression. Data are presented as mean \pm SEM (one-way ANOVA with *post hoc* Tukey test used for pairwise comparisons). * indicates p-value <0.05 ; ** indicate p-value <0.01 ; *** indicate p-value <0.001 ; **** indicate p-value <0.0001 ; and ns indicates no significant difference.

$p < 0.01$). TZP at medium (1.06-fold) and high doses (0.853-fold) significantly reduced Drp1 compared to induction ($p < 0.01$), with no significant differences between doses. Overall, TZP mitigated the diabetes-induced increases in Fis1 and Drp1 gene expression.

The effect of TZP on hepatic tissue histopathology

Light microscopic examinations of hepatic tissues revealed that the control group showed normal hepatic lobule cytoarchitecture, characterized by a normal hepatic cord, central vein, hepatic triad, hepatocyte, and sinusoidal organization, as illustrated in Fig. 5A. The histopathological figures of the induction group showed severe hepatitis with marked dilation of the central and portal veins, severe focal hemorrhage, moderate sinusoidal dilata-

tion with congestion, and minimal infiltration of mononuclear leukocytes (Fig. 5B). Other figures revealed severe dilation of the central vein with congestion, marked sinusoidal dilation with congestion, and minimal infiltration of mononuclear leukocytes, in addition to numerous sinusoidal lipofuscin-laden macrophages and severe fatty degeneration with atrophy of hepatocytes (Fig. 5C). Almost all histopathological figures of low-dose TZP of the liver showed a normal appearance of the central and portal veins, with mild sinusoidal dilation, infiltration of mononuclear leukocytes, and mild peri-central atrophy of the hepatic cords. There were a few sinusoidal stellate cells (fat-storing cells or leptocytes) (Fig. 5D). All histopathological figures of medium-dose TZP of the liver were similar to those of the control group (Fig. 5E). All histopathological figures of high-dose TZP of the liver showed normal cytoarchitecture of hepatic lobules (Fig. 5F).

Figure 5. Representative H&E-stained liver sections. Tirzepatide preserved hepatic cytoarchitecture and reduced inflammatory infiltration in a dose-dependent manner, consistent with its modulation of oxidative stress and mitochondrial dynamics. Histopathological scores are shown in the accompanying histogram. A) Normal control group: at low power, it shows the normal appearance of the central vein (V), the normal arrangement of hepatic cords (red arrows), and normal sinusoids. At high power, it shows normal hepatocytes (H), sinusoids (S), and lining endothelial cells. B and C) Induction group: at low power, it shows severe dilation of the central vein (C) and portal vein (P), normal hepatic cords with severe focal hemorrhage (red arrows), sinusoidal dilation, and slight infiltration of leukocytes (black arrows). At high power, it shows sinusoidal dilation with congestion (red arrows) and minimal hepatocyte degeneration. D) Low-dose TZP group: at low power, it exhibits mild atrophy of acini and slight degeneration of islet cells; at high power, it shows minimal degeneration of islet cells without necrosis. E) Medium-dose TZP group: at low power, it appears normal with hepatic cords (arrows) and the central vein (V); at high power, it shows normal hepatic cords and sinusoids (S). F) High-dose TZP group: at low power, it displays a normal appearance of the central vein (V) and hepatic cords (arrows); at high power, it exhibits normal hepatocytes (H) and sinusoids (S). G) Histogram of histopathological score. H&E stain at 10× and 40× magnification (five fields per slide at ×40).

Discussion

Diabetes is a chronic, systemic metabolic disorder marked by hyperglycemia and changes in carbohydrate, protein, and lipid metabolism (Dilworth et al. 2021). Mitochondria serve as a complex, dynamic network that constantly undergoes fusion and fission events, referred to as mitochondrial dynamics. Mitochondrial dynamics serve as a crucial quality control mechanism for retaining the mitochondrial population, which is essential for the stability of mitochondrial DNA, respiratory efficiency, and cellular

stress response (Chan 2012). Elevated glucose concentrations can damage complexes I and III, leading to ATP depletion, increased release of mitochondrial ROS, subsequent lipid peroxidation, glycation modification of associated proteins, and higher production of pro-apoptotic factors, including cytochrome c and apoptosis-inducing factor (Wei and Szeto 2019).

Excessive fat intake (50% of total energy) over three days negatively impacts mitochondrial health in skeletal muscle by altering gene expression related to the electron transport chain, mitochondrial biogenesis, and key regu-

lators such as PGC-1 α and PGC-1 β (Sparks et al. 2005). Administering an HFD to mice for 8 or 16 weeks has been shown to cause reduced fasting glucose and impaired glucose tolerance, along with a decrease in mitochondrial quantity, ATP production, and mitochondrial membrane potential in skeletal muscle (Xu et al. 2019).

Individuals with T2DM frequently exhibit increased expression of the fission-related protein DRP1, coupled with decreased expression of the fusion-associated proteins MFN2 and OPA1 (Hong et al. 2024). This results in increased mitochondrial fission and impaired removal of damaged mitochondria. Defects in mitochondrial structure and function are now acknowledged as significant contributors to the intracellular pathophysiology of diabetes. Mitochondrial dynamics link insulin resistance and mitochondrial dysfunction, contributing to the pathophysiology of T2DM. Along with the growth and expansion of the mitochondrial network and the improvement of mitochondrial dynamics, insulin sensitivity increased, resulting in the activation of the IRS1–AKT pathway and the stimulation of GLUT4 translocation (Lin et al. 2018). Maintaining appropriate mitochondrial fission and fusion dynamics is essential for cellular health. Nutrient overload – as shown in hyperglycemic or diabetic states – disrupts mitochondrial dynamics and induces oxidative stress. Direct intervention in mitochondrial dynamics may offer a potential therapeutic approach for addressing insulin resistance and enhancing blood glucose levels in diabetic patients (Chen et al. 2023).

In our study, we investigated mitochondrial dysfunction in diabetes mellitus, with a focus on liver tissue. Hepatic mitochondrial dysfunction has a complex relationship with the improper metabolism of glucose and lipids in diabetes and may serve as the underlying cause of hepatic insulin resistance (Jelenik and Roden 2013). The effect of hyperglycemia-induced mitochondrial dysfunction in the liver is essential in liver injury (Dey and Swaminathan 2010). An HFD administered to rodents was reported to influence respiratory capacity, ROS formation, fatty acid beta-oxidation, and the inhibition of mitochondrial ADP/ATP translocators, as well as the control of kinases implicated in carbohydrate and lipid metabolism (Dey and Swaminathan 2010). Adult rats subjected to HFD for seven weeks demonstrated obesity, hepatic steatosis, insulin resistance, diminished respiratory capacity, and enhanced oxidative stress in liver mitochondria. These findings imply that modifications within the mitochondrial compartment due to an HFD are linked to the onset of insulin resistance and ectopic fat accumulation in the liver, indicating mitochondrial dysfunction (Raffaella et al. 2008). The effect of STZ-induced diabetes on liver mitochondria showed elevated ROS at the electron transport chain, which is the primary origin of mitochondrial ROS production (Kristal et al. 1997).

TZP is a unique injectable medication approved for the treatment of T2DM that targets the GIP and GLP-1 receptors, effectively reducing blood glucose, hemoglobin A1c, and body weight. It has the potential to become a

leading antidiabetic drug (Tall Bull et al. 2022). This study examined the impact of different doses of TZP on genes involved in mitochondrial dynamics related to T2DM, using a diabetic rat model induced by HFD/STZ. The results showed increases in body weight, fat, blood sugar, cholesterol, and triglycerides in diabetic rats. Key features of T2DM include mitochondrial fragmentation, excessive ROS, and dysfunctional mitochondria (Zhan et al. 2015). These studies all support the idea that prolonged hyperglycemia causes mitochondrial fission (Wang et al. 2012).

The study found that HFD/STZ-induced diabetes altered the expression of mitochondrial fission and fusion genes, increased serum glucose, and decreased insulin. This correlates with other research showing that STZ-induced diabetes causes oxidative stress, damaging pancreatic beta cells and reducing insulin levels (Peyravi et al. 2020). The results of the present study show a significant increase in Fis1 gene expression in the induction group compared to the control group, which is consistent with a previous study indicating that in the HFD/STZ-diabetic group, the mRNA levels of Fis1 increased (Lin et al. 2018).

The results of the present study show a significant increase in Drp1 gene expression in the induction group compared to the control group, which is parallel with other studies (Peyravi et al. 2020). A recent study showed that a 10-week consumption of HFD led to an increase in the expression of Drp1 and Fis1 (Jahangiri et al. 2025). Another study has shown that an increase in the fission process has also been identified in the livers of genetically obese and diet-induced obese mice (Lionetti et al. 2014). Drp1 is essential for mitochondrial fission, acting as a GTPase that moves from the cytosol to the mitochondrial membrane to facilitate the division of mitochondria. This process is associated with a temporary decrease in the mitochondrial membrane potential (Taguchi et al. 2007). Fis1 was the first adaptor for Drp1 described in mammalian cells. Fis1 is a crucial part of the process that recruits Drp1 to the mitochondrial outer membrane, where Fis1 acts as a receptor (Losón et al. 2013). The current study shows increased gene expression of Fis1 during induction, which plays a role in mitochondrial fission by facilitating the recruitment of Drp1 from the cytoplasm. As a result, this led to an increase in Drp1 gene expression (Yoon et al. 2003). It forms assemblies (foci) that mainly associate with the mitochondrial surface, typically at sites of tubule constriction, ultimately leading to the fission of the two lipid membrane bilayers (Yoon et al. 2003). Overexpression of fission-related Drp1 and Fis1 caused mitochondrial fragmentation, increased mitochondrial division, and impaired removal of damaged mitochondria (Zerihun et al. 2023). This study demonstrates that TZP significantly reduces Fis1 gene expression across all treatment groups and decreases Drp1 gene expression at medium and high doses, but not at lower doses. This is the first evidence of TZP's impact on mitochondrial fission genes. By down-regulating Drp1 and Fis1, TZP reduces oxidative stress and liver dysfunction associated with excessive fat intake, thereby protecting against liver steatosis.

In our study, we found a significant decrease in Mfn1 gene expression in the induction group compared to the control. These results are aligned with a previous study, which showed that Mfn1 gene expression was significantly lower in the HFD/STZ-diabetic group compared to the healthy control group (Xu et al. 2015). The study found that Mfn1 gene expression increased significantly across all TZP treatment groups, exhibiting a dose-response pattern. Conversely, Mfn2 expression decreased notably in the induction group compared to controls, aligning with previous research (Peyravi et al. 2020). Another study indicated that patients with T2DM exhibit reduced Mfn2 expression in skeletal muscle compared to control participants (Bach et al. 2005). Another study showed a decrease in Mfn2 gene expression in the skeletal muscle of obese Zucker rats (Bach et al. 2003). Another study indicated that cardiac MFN2 expression decreases in rats with diabetes. The suppression of Mfn2 resulted in morphological and functional fragmentation of the mitochondrial network (Jorge et al. 2013). Mfn2 expression is essential for mitochondrial metabolism by maintaining mitochondrial network structure. Reduced MFN2 levels increase ROS, interfere with insulin signaling, and may lead to insulin resistance, which could explain certain metabolic changes associated with obesity and diabetes (Bach et al. 2005).

Mfn1 and Mfn2 are crucial for mitochondrial health, regulating fission and fusion, and supporting glucose-stimulated insulin secretion by maintaining mitochondrial DNA integrity. Their deletion in β -cells leads to reduced mitochondrial DNA, disrupted structure, impaired respiration, and glucose intolerance (Sidarala et al. 2022). This study is the first to show that TZP influences the expression of the mitochondrial fusion gene Mfn2. Higher doses of TZP (medium and high) significantly increase Mfn2 levels compared to the induction group, while lower doses do not. These results suggest that medium and high doses of TZP promote Mfn2 expression, which is involved in mitochondrial fusion. The fusion process involves tethering, docking, and merging of mitochondria, with Mfn2 playing a key role in the initial tethering through GTP-dependent conformational changes. Additionally, OPA1 is essential for maintaining mitochondrial structure (Olichon et al. 2003).

Our study found that Opa1 gene expression significantly decreased in the induction group compared to the control, consistent with previous research showing similar declines in the heart muscle of T2DM rats (Zafaranih et al. 2018). Another recent study indicated that Opa1 expression was lower in the livers of diabetic mice compared to the control mice (Wang et al. 2022). Our study found that Opa1 gene expression increased significantly in the high and medium doses of TZP compared to the induction group, while the low dose showed no difference. TZP enhances outer mitochondrial membrane fusion by upregulating MFN, and increased Opa1 supports inner mitochondrial membrane fusion via oligomer formation and GTP hydrolysis.

The overexpression of fusion-related proteins (Mfn1/Mfn2) and the suppression of fission-related proteins (Drp1/Fis1) enhance the mitochondrial network and re-

verse insulin resistance by activating the IRS1-Akt pathway and aiding the translocation of GLUT1/GLUT4 to the cell membrane (Lin et al. 2018). Elevated glucose levels in T2DM enhance ROS generation (Newsholme et al. 2016). Excessive caloric consumption leads to an accumulation of intramyocellular lipids (Hegarty et al. 2002). Increased ROS generation, oxidative stress, and mitochondrial impairments in skeletal muscle (Bonnard et al. 2008). ROS serves as an essential mediator in the dysregulation of mitochondrial activity and T2DM. Changes in mitochondrial shape and dynamics are necessary to elevate ROS in hyperglycemic conditions (Yu et al. 2006). Mitochondria undergo rapid fragmentation, accompanied by increased ROS production, in response to hyperglycemia. Hyperglycemia also leads to mitochondrial disruption in various cell types, including cardiac, vascular, and hepatic cells (Yu et al. 2006).

In T2DM, increased ROS production and lipid peroxidation, along with reduced glutathione levels and antioxidant enzyme activity, are observed (Kumawat et al. 2013). The study's data demonstrated that the induction group led to an increase in lipid peroxidation, as indicated by an elevated MDA level and reduced GSH levels, which is consistent with previous studies (Gilani et al. 2021). MDA is a breakdown product of lipid peroxidation, caused by free radical damage to unsaturated fatty acids, and serves as an indirect marker for oxidative stress. Since direct measurement of ROS is difficult, MDA levels offer a useful biomarker for oxidative stress (Sunita et al. 2020). Augmented DRP1 activity promotes mitochondrial fragmentation and dysfunction, leading to reduced ATP production and increased ROS generation. Elevated ROS causes lipid peroxidation (increased MDA levels) and exhaustion of antioxidant defenses like GSH, resulting in oxidative stress. This disrupts mitochondrial dynamics and creates a harmful cycle of ROS production that worsens mitochondrial damage (Tsushima et al. 2018). Mitochondrial dynamics, controlled by fusion and fission, typically balance each other. The study showed that HFD/STZ treatment shifted this balance by increasing proteins related to mitochondrial fission.

This study found that TZP treatment significantly reduced serum MDA levels in a dose-dependent manner, consistent with recent research indicating TZP's beneficial effects in diabetic nephropathy (Yang et al. 2025). The balance of antioxidants, such as GSH, and oxidative stress markers suggests mitochondrial dysfunction – characterized by increased fission (upregulation of Drp1 and Fis1) and decreased fusion (Mfn1, Mfn2, and Opa1). Elevated Drp1 also promotes mitochondrial membrane permeabilization via Bax/Bak, increasing ROS production (Alathary and Kadhim 2024). In this investigation, administration of medium and high doses of TZP resulted in a statistically significant elevation in serum GSH levels relative to the induction group, aligning with findings from recent scholarly research (Tian et al. 2025). Another recent study demonstrated that TZP increased the GSH level in rats with renal ischemia/reperfusion damage (Alkhafeji and Janabi 2025). The antioxidant criteria of TZP regard-

ing tissue injury, including cardiac tissue and nephrotic tissue, are well-documented (Hegab et al. 2024).

The study found that STZ/HFD increased blood glucose, insulin, and HOMA-IR levels. TZP improved glucose tolerance, lowered insulin and HOMA-IR, and reduced fasting blood glucose in diabetic rats, aligning with recent research (Guo et al. 2023). Significant improvements in pancreatic beta-cell activity and insulin sensitivity were observed with TZP (Lee et al. 2023). GIP and GLP-1 receptor activation exhibited a synergistic effect on insulin signaling, surpassing the effects of monotherapy (Min and Bain 2021). TZP demonstrated superior efficacy in controlling fasting blood glucose compared to a GLP-1R agonist alone. The SURPASS-2 study indicated that TZP more effectively reduced glycated hemoglobin and fasting serum glucose levels than semaglutide across all doses (5, 10, and 15 mg) (Frías et al. 2021).

In our current study, the histopathological changes observed in the liver tissue of the STZ/HFD diabetes model indicate T2DM-related hepatic impairment, characterized by hepatocyte damage and alterations in liver morphology. HFD-fed STZ-induced rats exhibited fatty degeneration with necrosis, blood vessel dilation, and lobular inflammation. These findings are consistent with previous studies, which have demonstrated that HFD-fed STZ-induced rat models display fatty liver and histological alterations, including lipid accumulation and lobular inflammation (Guo et al. 2018). Fragmented mitochondria impair β -oxidation and mitochondrial function, causing hepatocyte fat accumulation. This reduces oxidative capacity and increases ROS, activating stellate cells and pro-inflammatory cy-

tokines. Liver inflammation is evidenced by elevated MDA and decreased SOD. Elevated hepatic fatty acids enhance mitochondrial ROS production, leading to lipid peroxidation and structural damage. Hyperglycemia and hyperlipidemia further exacerbate mitochondrial dysfunction, causing membrane permeabilization, ATP decline, and hepatocyte apoptosis or necrosis (Serviddio et al. 2010). The histopathological analysis revealed that low-dose TZP had a slight improvement in liver tissue. At the same time, medium and high doses resembled a normal liver structure, characterized by normal hepatocytes and reduced signs of damage, including blood vessel dilation, fatty degeneration, necrosis, and inflammation. A recent study also indicated that TZP treatment significantly reduced fat accumulation and inflammation in HFD rats (Liang et al. 2025). A recent study found that TZP has significant hepatoprotective effects, reducing liver fat and inflammation (Iwamoto et al. 2024). Its benefits are linked to decreasing DRP1 levels, which may prevent liver damage. Additionally, TZP helps mitigate T2DM-related liver injury by lowering lipid peroxidation and oxidative stress markers, such as MDA, while increasing antioxidants. It also reduces glucose, cholesterol, triglycerides, and VLDL levels and promotes mitochondrial fusion and insulin signaling in rats on a high-fat diet supplemented with streptozotocin.

In line with the schematic presented in Fig. 6, our data demonstrate that HFD/STZ-induced T2DM disrupts hepatic mitochondrial homeostasis by shifting the balance toward excessive fission, as evidenced by elevated Drp1 and Fis1 expression alongside reduced Mfn1, Mfn2, and Opa1 levels. This molecular profile coincided with in-

Figure 6. Proposed mechanism of tirzepatide (TZP)-mediated gene expression changes of hepatic mitochondrial dynamics in HFD/STZ-induced type 2 diabetic rats. Schematic representation comparing the pathological state in untreated T2DM (left) with the post-treatment state following TZP administration (right). In T2DM, hyperglycemia and insulin resistance promote excessive mitochondrial fission via upregulation of dynamin-related protein 1 (Drp1) and fission protein 1 (Fis1), with concurrent downregulation of fusion mediators mitofusin 1 (Mfn1), mitofusin 2 (Mfn2), and optic atrophy 1 (Opa1). This imbalance leads to mitochondrial fragmentation, increased generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS), elevated malondialdehyde (MDA) levels, reduced glutathione (GSH) levels, and histological evidence of steatosis, inflammation, and sinusoidal dilation. TZP treatment activates GLP-1 and GIP receptors, thereby improving insulin sensitivity, reducing oxidative stress, and restoring mitochondrial fusion through the upregulation of Mfn1, Mfn2, and Opa1, while suppressing Drp1 and Fis1. These changes decrease ROS production, enhance antioxidant defense, normalize MDA and GSH levels, and preserve hepatic architecture.

creased ROS generation, elevated MDA, depleted GSH, and histopathological features of steatosis, inflammatory infiltration, and sinusoidal dilation. Tirzepatide administration reversed these alterations, restoring the fusion-fission equilibrium through the upregulation of Mfn1, Mfn2, and Opa1, and the suppression of Drp1 and Fis1. These changes were accompanied by a reduction in oxidative stress markers, normalization of antioxidant capacity, and preservation of hepatic architecture. Collectively, these findings support a model in which tirzepatide exerts hepatoprotective effects in T2DM by dual activation of the incretin receptors, leading to improved insulin sensitivity, attenuation of oxidative stress, and restoration of mitochondrial network integrity.

Study limitations

While our findings demonstrate that tirzepatide modulates hepatic mitochondrial fusion-fission gene expression and alleviates oxidative stress in diabetic rats, the study is limited to mRNA-level analyses and histological observations. Protein-level confirmation and functional assays of mitochondrial activity (respiration, ATP generation, membrane potential, ultrastructural electron microscopy) were not performed. These approaches are essential for validating the transcriptional changes reported here and for establishing direct mechanistic links between tirzepatide treatment and mitochondrial function. Future studies incorporating these methods will be crucial to elucidate the hepatoprotective potential of tirzepatide fully.

Although our current study evaluates insulin resistance using HOMA-IR, we acknowledge the limitations of this approach, particularly the lack of direct measurements of insulin sensitivity, such as those obtained through hyperinsulinemic-euglycemic clamp techniques. Consequently, caution should be exercised when interpreting elevated fasting insulin levels in the absence of dynamic assessments. Furthermore, mitophagy was not directly measured; thus, our findings should be regarded as gene expression trends indicative of a potential shift toward enhanced cellular mitochondrial balance, rather than definitive evidence of alterations in hyperfusion or autophagic flux. Future studies will incorporate the quantification of mitophagy markers and ultrastructural analyses to definitively rule out adverse hyperfusion. Morphological data suggest a trend toward a more fused, functionally competent mitochondrial network; however, confirmation of changes in mitochondrial dynamics requires direct functional assays.

Conclusion

In hyperglycemic conditions, increased ROS production leads to changes in mitochondrial shape, with the inhibition of mitochondrial fission preventing fluctuations in ROS levels. TZP improves mitochondrial function by promoting fusion (via Mfn1, Mfn2, Opa1) and inhibiting

fission (via Fis1 and Drp1) in the liver. This suggests that TZP could be a potential treatment for metabolic diseases associated with mitochondrial dysfunction, as it ameliorates diabetes-related defects in hepatic mitochondrial morphology by promoting mitochondrial fusion and decreasing mitochondrial fission in hepatic tissue.

Future research enabled by the insights gained herein will benefit from a multimodal assessment of mitochondrial dynamics, careful mechanistic dissection, and comprehensive functional validation to robustly characterize how emerging therapies, such as tirzepatide, impact the health of subcellular organelles in metabolic disease.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have no relevant financial or non-financial interests to disclose.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

Experiments on animals: The study was approved by the Scientific Committee of Mustansiriya University's College of Pharmacy, Pharmacology, and Toxicology Department (Approval number: 87, Reference number: 190, Date: 8 October 2024), following the American Veterinary Association Guidelines.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

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Author contributions

Conceptualization, investigation, and manuscript preparation: Fakhir SD, Arif IS, Waheed HJ. Supervision: Arif IS, Waheed HJ. Statistical analysis and review of final results: Waheed HJ. Manuscript review and editing: Fakhir SD, Arif IS, Waheed HJ. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Author ORCIDs

Shams Dhiaa Fakhir <https://orcid.org/0009-0004-1860-1055>

Inam Sameh Arif <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9194-1919>

Huda Jaber Waheed <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8491-8334>

Data availability

Fakhir, S. D. (2025). Tirzepatide and Hepatic Mitochondrial Balance [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16970105>.

References

- Abd-Allahussain GK, Alatrakji M, Ahmed SJ, Fawzi HA (2024) Efficacy of oral insulin nanoparticles for the management of hyperglycemia in a rat model of diabetes induced with streptozotocin. *Journal of Medicine and Life* 17: 217–225. <https://doi.org/10.25122/jml-2023-0355>
- Al Ojaimi M, Salah A, El-Hattab AW (2022) Mitochondrial Fission and Fusion: Molecular Mechanisms, Biological Functions, and Related Disorders. *Membranes* 12. <https://doi.org/10.3390/membranes12090893>
- Alathary AJ, Kadhim ZJ (2024) Tirzepatide pr eptide protects against hepatic o tects against hepatic oxidativ xidative stress in high-fat induced ess in high-fat induced obesity in male rats. *Maaen Journal for Medical Sciences* 3: 136–143. <https://doi.org/10.55810/2789-9136.1053>
- Alkhafaji GA, Janabi AM (2025) GIP/GLP-1 dual agonist tirzepatide ameliorates renal ischemia/reperfusion damage in rats. *International Journal of Applied Pharmaceutics* 17: 165–173. <https://doi.org/10.22159/ijap.2025v17i2.53156>
- Alshehri GH, Al-kuraishy HM, Waheed HJ, Al-Gareeb AI, Faheem SA, Alexiou A, Papadakis M, El-Saber Batiha G (2025) Tirzepatide: a novel therapeutic approach for Alzheimer's disease. *Metabolic Brain Disease* 40. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11011-025-01649-z>
- Atia YA, Mohammed ST, Abdullah SS, Abbas AS, Fawzi HA (2024) Effects of subclinical hypothyroidism in type II diabetes mellitus patients on biochemical, coagulation, and fibrinolysis status. *Journal of Advanced Pharmaceutical Technology and Research* 15: 130–134. https://doi.org/10.4103/JAPTR.JAPTR_89_24
- Bach D, Naon D, Pich S, Soriano FX, Vega N, Rieusset J, Laville M, Guillet C, Boirie Y, Wallberg-Henriksson H, Manco M, Calvani M, Castagneto M, Palacín M, Mingrone G, Zierath JR, Vidal H, Zorzano A (2005) Expression of Mfn2, the Charcot-Marie-Tooth Neuropathy Type 2A Gene, in human skeletal muscle: Effects of Type 2 diabetes, obesity, weight loss, and the regulatory role of tumor necrosis factor α and Interleukin-6. *Diabetes* 54: 2685–2693. <https://doi.org/10.2337/diabetes.54.9.2685>
- Bach D, Pich S, Soriano FX, Vega N, Baumgartner B, Oriola J, Daugaard JR, Lloberas J, Camps M, Zierath JR, Rabasa-Lhoret R, Wallberg-Henriksson H, Laville M, Palacín M, Vidal H, Rivera F, Brand M, Zorzano A (2003) Mitofusin-2 determines mitochondrial network architecture and mitochondrial metabolism. A novel regulatory mechanism altered in obesity. *Journal of Biological Chemistry* 278: 17190–17197. <https://doi.org/10.1074/jbc.M212754200>
- Bhatti JS, Bhatti GK, Reddy PH (2017) Mitochondrial dysfunction and oxidative stress in metabolic disorders – A step towards mitochondria based therapeutic strategies. *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta: Molecular Basis of Disease* 1863: 1066–1077. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbadis.2016.11.010>
- Binh DV, Dung NTK, Thao L, Nhi N, Chi P (2013) Macro-and micro-vascular complications of diabetes induced by high-fat diet and low-dose streptozotocin injection in rats model. *International Journal of Diabetes Research* 2: 50–55. <https://doi.org/10.15625/0866-7160/v35n3.3396>
- Bonnard C, Durand A, Peyrol S, Chanseaux E, Chauvin MA, Morio B, Vidal H, Rieusset J (2008) Mitochondrial dysfunction results from oxidative stress in the skeletal muscle of diet-induced insulin-resistant mice. *Journal of Clinical Investigation* 118: 789–800. <https://doi.org/10.1172/JCI32601>
- Boyman L, Karbowski M, Lederer WJ (2020) Regulation of mitochondrial ATP production: Ca(2+) Signaling and quality control. *Trends in Molecular Medicine* 26: 21–39. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molmed.2019.10.007>
- Chan DC (2012) Fusion and fission: Interlinked processes critical for mitochondrial health. *Annual Review of Genetics* 46: 265–287. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-genet-110410-132529>
- Chen G, Wang R, Chen H, Wu L, Ge RS, Wang Y (2016) Gossypol ameliorates liver fibrosis in diabetic rats induced by high-fat diet and streptozocin. *Life Sciences* 149: 58–64. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lfs.2016.02.044>
- Chen W, Zhao H, Li Y (2023) Mitochondrial dynamics in health and disease: mechanisms and potential targets. *Signal Transduction and Targeted Therapy* 8: e333. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41392-023-01547-9>
- Chiang JL, Maahs DM, Garvey KC, Hood KK, Laffel LM, Weinzimer SA, Wolfsdorf JI, Schatz D (2018) Type 1 diabetes in children and adolescents: A position statement by the American Diabetes Association. *Diabetes Care* 41: 2026–2044. <https://doi.org/10.2337/dci18-0023>
- Chou CY, Hsu DY, Chou CH (2023) Predicting the onset of diabetes with machine learning methods. *Journal of Personalized Medicine* 13. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jpm13030406>
- Dey A, Swaminathan K (2010) Hyperglycemia-induced mitochondrial alterations in liver. *Life Sciences* 87: 197–214. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lfs.2010.06.007>
- Dilworth L, Facey A, Omoruyi F (2021) Diabetes mellitus and its metabolic complications: The role of adipose tissues. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences* 22: e7644. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms22147644>
- Eisner V, Picard M, Hajnóczky G (2018) Mitochondrial dynamics in adaptive and maladaptive cellular stress responses. *Nature Cell Biology* 20: 755–765. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41556-018-0133-0>
- El K, Dourous JD, Willard FS, Novikoff A, Sargsyan A, Perez-Tilve D, Wainscott DB, Yang B, Chen A, Wothe D, Coupland C, Tschöp MH, Finan B, D'Alessio DA, Sloop KW, Müller TD, Campbell JE (2023) The incretin co-agonist tirzepatide requires GIPR for hormone secretion from human islets. *Nature Metabolism* 5: 945–954. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s42255-023-00811-0>
- Fadhil AFS, Kamal YM, Waheed HJ (2024) The hepatoprotective effect of *Glycyrrhiza glabra* roots extract against amiodarone induced hepatotoxicity in male rats. *Iraqi Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences* 33: 190–196. <https://doi.org/10.31351/vol33iss2pp190-196>
- Frías JP, Davies MJ, Rosenstock J, Pérez Manghi FC, Fernández Landó L, Bergman BK, Liu B, Cui X, Brown K (2021) Tirzepatide versus semaglutide once weekly in patients with Type 2 diabetes. *The New England Journal of Medicine* 385: 503–515. <https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMoa2107519>
- Gao S, Hu J (2021) Mitochondrial fusion: The machineries in and out. *Trends in Cell Biology* 31: 62–74. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tcb.2020.09.008>
- Gastaldelli A, Cusi K, Pettiti M, Hardies J, Miyazaki Y, Berria R, Buzzigoli E, Sironi AM, Cersosimo E, Ferrannini E, DeFronzo RA (2007) Relationship between hepatic/visceral fat and hepatic insulin resistance in nondiabetic and type 2 diabetic subjects. *Gastroenterology* 133: 496–506. <https://doi.org/10.1053/j.gastro.2007.04.068>
- Gilani SJ, Bin-Jumah MN, Al-Abbasi FA, Nadeem MS, Afzal M, Sayyed N, Kazmi I (2021) Fustin ameliorates elevated levels of leptin, adi-

- ponectin, serum TNF- α , and intracellular oxidative free radicals in high-fat diet and streptozotocin-induced diabetic rats. *ACS Omega* 6: 26098–26107. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsomega.1c03068>
- Green A, Hossain T, Eckmann DM (2022) Mitochondrial dynamics involves molecular and mechanical events in motility, fusion and fission. *Frontiers in Cell and Developmental Biology* 10: e1010232. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fcell.2022.1010232>
- Guo X, Lei M, Zhao J, Wu M, Ren Z, Yang X, Ouyang C, Liu X, Liu C, Chen Q (2023) Tirzepatide ameliorates spatial learning and memory impairment through modulation of aberrant insulin resistance and inflammation response in diabetic rats. *Frontiers in Pharmacology* 14: e1146960. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphar.2023.1146960>
- Guo XX, Wang Y, Wang K, Ji BP, Zhou F (2018) Stability of a type 2 diabetes rat model induced by high-fat diet feeding with low-dose streptozotocin injection. *Journal of Zhejiang University Science B* 19: 559–569. <https://doi.org/10.1631/jzus.B1700254>
- Hamid S, Sahib HB, Fawzi HA, Nori AY (2018) Medication adherence and glycemic control in newly diagnosed diabetic patients. *International Journal of Research in Pharmaceutical Sciences* 9: 816–820.
- Hammadi NA, almullahummadi YMK, Waheed HJ (2025) Nebivolol effect on oxidative biomarkers in Tamoxifen-Induced hepatotoxicity in female white albino rats: In Vivo study. *Al Mustansiriyah Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences* 25: 203–211. <https://doi.org/10.32947/ajps.v25i2.1157>
- Hegab, II, El-Horany HE, Abd-Ellatif RN, Nasef NA, Okasha AH, Emam MN, Hassan S, Elseady WS, Radwan DA, ElEsawy RO, Hafez YM, Hassan ME, Mansour NM, Abdelkader GE, Fouda MH, Abd El Maged AM, Abdallah HM (2024) Adropin/Tirzepatide combination mitigates cardiac metabolic aberrations in a rat model of polycystic ovarian syndrome, implicating the role of the AKT/GSK3 β /NF- κ B/NLRP3 pathway. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences* 26. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms26010001>
- Hegarty BD, Cooney GJ, Kraegen EW, Furler SM (2002) Increased efficiency of fatty acid uptake contributes to lipid accumulation in skeletal muscle of high fat-fed insulin-resistant rats. *Diabetes* 51: 1477–1484. <https://doi.org/10.2337/diabetes.51.5.1477>
- Hong WL, Huang H, Zeng X, Duan CY (2024) Targeting mitochondrial quality control: new therapeutic strategies for major diseases. *Military Medical Research* 11: 1–59. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40779-024-00556-1>
- Iwamoto Y, Kimura T, Dan K, Iwamoto H, Sanada J, Fushimi Y, Katakura Y, Shimoda M, Yamasaki Y, Nogami Y, Shirakiya Y, Nakanishi S, Mune T, Kaku K, Kaneto H (2024) Tirzepatide, a dual glucose-dependent insulinotropic polypeptide/glucagon-like peptide 1 receptor agonist, exhibits favourable effects on pancreatic β -cells and hepatic steatosis in obese type 2 diabetic db/db mice. *Diabetes, Obesity and Metabolism* 26: 5982–5994. <https://doi.org/10.1111/dom.15972>
- Jahangiri M, Shahrbanian S, Gharakhanlou R (2025) High intensity interval training alters gene expression linked to mitochondrial biogenesis and dynamics in high fat diet fed rats. *Scientific Reports* 15: e5442. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-025-86767-5>
- Jawad AN, Kadhim KA, Ali ZH, Fawzi HA, Alzajaji QB (2025) Association between a glucagon-like peptide-1 receptor genetic polymorphism and therapeutic response to sitagliptin in type 2 diabetic patients: An observational study. *International Journal of Diabetes in Developing Countries*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13410-025-01537-3>
- Jelenik T, Roden M (2013) Mitochondrial plasticity in obesity and diabetes mellitus. *Antioxidants & Redox Signaling* 19: 258–268. <https://doi.org/10.1089/ars.2012.4910>
- Jorge L, Paulini J, Silva C, Rampaso R, Luiz R, Lima W, Scavasin G, Schor N (2013) Abstract 613: Exercise training improves cardiac mitofusin 2 expression in diabetes. *Hypertension* 62: A613–A613. https://doi.org/10.1161/hyp.62.suppl_1.A613
- Kadhim HM, Kadhim YM, Fawzi HA, Abdul Khalik ZM, Jawad AM, Ghédira K (2025) Bioassay-Guided isolation and active compounds identification of the antidiabetic fractions of *Centaurea calcitrapa* extract and the predicted interaction mechanism. *Molecules* 30. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules30112394>
- Kapoor R, Kakkar P (2012) Protective role of morin, a flavonoid, against high glucose induced oxidative stress mediated apoptosis in primary rat hepatocytes. *PLoS ONE* 7: e41663. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0041663>
- Karwi YG, Arif IS, Al-Ezzi MI (2018) The potential protective effect of metformin on selective cardiac biomarkers in diabetic male rats. *Al Mustansiriyah Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences* 17: 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.32947/ajps.v17i1.65>
- Kristal BS, Koopmans SJ, Jackson CT, Ikeno Y, Park BJ, Yu BP (1997) Oxidant-mediated repression of mitochondrial transcription in diabetic rats. *Free Radical Biology and Medicine* 22: 813–822. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0891-5849\(96\)00429-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0891-5849(96)00429-7)
- Kumawat M, Sharma TK, Singh I, Singh N, Ghalaut VS, Vardey SK, Shankar V (2013) Antioxidant enzymes and lipid peroxidation in Type 2 diabetes mellitus patients with and without nephropathy. *North American Journal of Medical Sciences* 5: 213–219. <https://doi.org/10.4103/1947-2714.109193>
- Lee CJ, Mao H, Thieu VT, Landó LF, Thomas MK (2023) Tirzepatide as monotherapy improved markers of beta-cell function and insulin sensitivity in Type 2 diabetes (SURPASS-1). *Journal of the Endocrine Society* 7: bvad056. <https://doi.org/10.1210/jendso/bvad056>
- Liang J, Liu H, Lv G, Chen X, Yang Z, Hu K, Sun H (2025) Exploring the molecular mechanisms of tirzepatide in alleviating metabolic dysfunction-associated fatty liver in mice through integration of metabolomics, lipidomics, and proteomics. *Lipids in Health and Disease* 24: 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12944-024-02416-2>
- Lin HY, Weng SW, Chang YH, Su YJ, Chang CM, Tsai CJ, Shen FC, Chuang JH, Lin TK, Liou CW, Lin CY, Wang PW (2018) The causal role of mitochondrial dynamics in regulating insulin resistance in diabetes: Link through mitochondrial reactive oxygen species. *Oxidative Medicine and Cellular Longevity* 2018: e7514383. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2018/7514383>
- Lionetti L, Mollica MP, Donizzetti I, Gifuni G, Sica R, Pignalosa A, Cavaliere G, Gaita M, De Filippo C, Zorzano A, Putti R (2014) High-lard and high-fish-oil diets differ in their effects on function and dynamic behaviour of rat hepatic mitochondria. *PLoS ONE* 9: e92753. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0092753>
- Livak KJ, Schmittgen TD (2001) Analysis of relative gene expression data using real-time quantitative PCR and the 2^{(-Delta Delta C(T))} Method. *Methods* 25: 402–408. <https://doi.org/10.1006/meth.2001.1262>
- Losón OC, Song Z, Chen H, Chan DC (2013) Fis1, Mff, MiD49, and MiD51 mediate Drp1 recruitment in mitochondrial fission. *Molecular Biology of the Cell* 24: 659–667. doi:10.1091/mbc.E12-10-0721. <https://doi.org/10.1091/mbc.e12-10-0721>
- Lu X, Xie Q, Pan X, Zhang R, Zhang X, Peng G, Zhang Y, Shen S, Tong N (2024) Type 2 diabetes mellitus in adults: pathogenesis, prevention and therapy. *Signal Transduction and Targeted Therapy* 9: e262. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41392-024-01951-9>

- Min T, Bain SC (2021) The role of tirzepatide, dual GIP and GLP-1 receptor agonist, in the management of Type 2 diabetes: The SURPASS clinical trials. *Diabetes Therapy* 12: 143–157. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13300-020-00981-0>
- Nair AB, Jacob S (2016) A simple practice guide for dose conversion between animals and human. *Journal of Basic and Clinical Pharmacy* 7: 27–31. <https://doi.org/10.4103/0976-0105.177703>
- Newsholme P, Cruzat VF, Keane KN, Carlessi R, de Bittencourt Jr PI (2016) Molecular mechanisms of ROS production and oxidative stress in diabetes. *Biochemical Journal* 473: 4527–4550. <https://doi.org/10.1042/BCJ20160503C>
- Ni HM, Williams JA, Ding WX (2015) Mitochondrial dynamics and mitochondrial quality control. *Redox Biology* 4: 6–13. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.redox.2014.11.006>
- Nunan AT, Jawad NK, Fawzi HA (2024) Biochemical study of the risk of diabetes, prediabetic and insulin resistance in car painters and its association with mercury exposure: A retrospective case-control study. *Toxicology Research* 13. <https://doi.org/10.1093/toxres/tae221>
- Obead Nk, Arif IS, Waheed HJ, Batiha GE-S (2025) Quercetin improves the histopathological changes of liver caused by interferon beta 1b-induced liver injury. *Al Mustansiriyah Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences* 25: 258–265. <https://doi.org/10.32947/ajps.v25i2.1153>
- Olichon A, Baricault L, Gas N, Guillou E, Valette A, Belenguer P, Lenaers G (2003) Loss of OPA1 perturbs the mitochondrial inner membrane structure and integrity, leading to cytochrome c release and apoptosis. *Journal of Biological Chemistry* 278: 7743–7746. <https://doi.org/10.1074/jbc.C200677200>
- Pang D, Laferrriere C (2020) Review of intraperitoneal injection of sodium pentobarbital as a method of euthanasia in laboratory rodents. *Journal of the American Association for Laboratory Animal Science* 59: e346. <https://doi.org/10.30802/AALAS-JAALAS-19-000081>
- Panos GD, Boeckler FM (2023) Statistical analysis in clinical and experimental medical research: Simplified guidance for authors and reviewers. *Drug Design, Development and Therapy* 17: 1959–1961. <https://doi.org/10.2147/DDDT.S427470>
- Percie du Sert N, Ahluwalia A, Alam S, Avey MT, Baker M, Browne WJ, Clark A, Cuthill IC, Dirnagl U, Emerson M, Garner P, Holgate ST, Howells DW, Hurst V, Karp NA, Lazic SE, Lidster K, MacCallum CJ, Macleod M, Pearl EJ, Petersen OH, Rawle F, Reynolds P, Rooney K, Sena ES, Silberberg SD, Steckler T, Würbel H (2020) Reporting animal research: Explanation and elaboration for the ARRIVE guidelines 2.0. *PLOS Biology* 18: e3000411. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.3000411>
- Pernas L, Scorrano L (2016) Mito-Morphosis: Mitochondrial fusion, fission, and cristae remodeling as key mediators of cellular function. *Annual Review of Physiology* 78: 505–531. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-physiol-021115-105011>
- Peyravi A, Yazdanpanahi N, Nayeri H, Hosseini SA (2020) The effect of endurance training with crocin consumption on the levels of MFN2 and DRP1 gene expression and glucose and insulin indices in the muscle tissue of diabetic rats. *Journal of Food Biochemistry* 44: e13125. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jfbc.13125>
- Pinti MV, Fink GK, Hathaway QA, Durr AJ, Kunovac A, Hollander JM (2019) Mitochondrial dysfunction in type 2 diabetes mellitus: an organ-based analysis. *American Journal of Physiology-Endocrinology and Metabolism* 316: E268–e285. <https://doi.org/10.1152/ajpendo.00314.2018>
- Raffaella C, Francesca B, Italia F, Marina P, Giovanna L, Susanna I (2008) Alterations in hepatic mitochondrial compartment in a model of obesity and insulin resistance. *Obesity (Silver Spring)* 16: 958–964. <https://doi.org/10.1038/oby.2008.10>
- Rovira-Llopis S, Bañuls C, Diaz-Morales N, Hernandez-Mijares A, Rocha M, Victor VM (2017) Mitochondrial dynamics in Type 2 diabetes: Pathophysiological implications. *Redox Biology* 11: 637–645. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.redox.2017.01.013>
- Sargsyan A, Herman MA (2019) Regulation of glucose production in the pathogenesis of Type 2 diabetes. *Current Diabetes Reports* 19: e77. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11892-019-1195-5>
- Serviddio G, Bellanti F, Sastre J, Vendemiale G, Altomare E (2010) Targeting mitochondria: A new promising approach for the treatment of liver diseases. *Current Medicinal Chemistry* 17: 2325–2337. <https://doi.org/10.2174/092986710791698530>
- Shan Z, Fa WH, Tian CR, Yuan CS, Jie N (2022) Mitophagy and mitochondrial dynamics in type 2 diabetes mellitus treatment. *Aging* 14: 2902–2919. <https://doi.org/10.18632/aging.203969>
- Sidarala V, Zhu J, Levi-D'Ancona E, Pearson GL, Reck EC, Walker EM, Kaufman BA, Soleimanpour SA (2022) Mitofusin 1 and 2 regulation of mitochondrial DNA content is a critical determinant of glucose homeostasis. *Nature Communications* 13: e2340. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-022-29945-7>
- Sparks LM, Xie H, Koza RA, Mynatt R, Hulver MW, Bray GA, Smith SR (2005) A high-fat diet coordinately downregulates genes required for mitochondrial oxidative phosphorylation in skeletal muscle. *Diabetes* 54: 1926–1933. <https://doi.org/10.2337/diabetes.54.7.1926>
- Sunita R, Sahidan S, Hidayat R (2020) Evaluation of malondialdehyde in Type 2 diabetes mellitus patients as oxidative stress markers in Bengkulu population. *Bioscientia Medicina: Journal of Biomedicine and Translational Research* 4: 45–54. <https://doi.org/10.32539/bsm.v4i3.146>
- Taguchi N, Ishihara N, Jofuku A, Oka T, Mihara K (2007) Mitotic phosphorylation of dynamin-related GTPase Drp1 participates in mitochondrial fission. *Journal of Biological Chemistry* 282: 11521–11529. <https://doi.org/10.1074/jbc.M607279200>
- Tall Bull S, Nuffer W, Trujillo JM (2022) Tirzepatide: A novel, first-in-class, dual GIP/GLP-1 receptor agonist. *Journal of Diabetes and its Complications* 36: e108332. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jdiacomp.2022.108332>
- Tian Y, Tian R, Juan H, Guo Y, Yan P, Cheng Y, Li R, Wang B (2025) GLP-1/GIP dual agonist tirzepatide normalizes diabetic nephropathy via PI3K/AKT mediated suppression of oxidative stress. *International Immunopharmacology* 146: e113877. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.intimp.2024.113877>
- Tsushima K, Bugger H, Wende AR, Soto J, Jenson GA, Tor AR, McGlaufflin R, Kenny HC, Zhang Y, Souvenir R, Hu XX, Sloan CL, Pereira RO, Lira VA, Spitzer KW, Sharp TL, Shoghi KI, Sparagna GC, Rog-Zielinska EA, Kohl P, Khalimonchuk O, Schaffer JE, Abel ED (2018) Mitochondrial reactive oxygen species in lipotoxic hearts induce post-translational modifications of AKAP121, DRP1, and OPA1 that promote mitochondrial fission. *Circulation Research* 122: 58–73. <https://doi.org/10.1161/CIRCRESAHA.117.311307>
- Underwood W, Anthony R (2020) AVMA guidelines for the euthanasia of animals: 2020 edition. Retrieved on March 2021: 2020–2021.
- Wai T, Langer T (2016) Mitochondrial dynamics and metabolic regulation. *Trends in Endocrinology and Metabolism* 27: 105–117. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tem.2015.12.001>

- Wang T, Chen Y, Li Y, Wang Z, Qiu C, Yang D, Chen K (2022) TRPV1 Protect against Hyperglycemia and Hyperlipidemia induced liver injury via OPA1 in diabetes. *Tohoku Journal of Experimental Medicine* 256: 131–139. <https://doi.org/10.1620/tjem.256.131>
- Wang W, Wang Y, Long J, Wang J, Haudek SB, Overbeek P, Chang BH, Schumacker PT, Danesh FR (2012) Mitochondrial fission triggered by hyperglycemia is mediated by ROCK1 activation in podocytes and endothelial cells. *Cell Metabolism* 15: 186–200. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cmet.2012.01.009>
- Wei PZ, Szeto CC (2019) Mitochondrial dysfunction in diabetic kidney disease. *Clinica Chimica Acta* 496: 108–116. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cca.2019.07.005>
- Xu D, Jiang Z, Sun Z, Wang L, Zhao G, Hassan HM, Fan S, Zhou W, Han S, Zhang L, Wang T (2019) Mitochondrial dysfunction and inhibition of myoblast differentiation in mice with high-fat-diet-induced pre-diabetes. *Journal of Cellular Physiology* 234: 7510–7523. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jcp.27512>
- Xu G, Liu B, Sun Y, Du Y, Snetselaar LG, Hu FB, Bao W (2018) Prevalence of diagnosed type 1 and type 2 diabetes among US adults in 2016 and 2017: population based study. *BMJ* 362: k1497. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.k1497>
- Xu Z, Zhang L, Li X, Jiang Z, Sun L, Zhao G, Zhou G, Zhang H, Shang J, Wang T (2015) Mitochondrial fusion/fission process involved in the improvement of catalpol on high glucose-induced hepatic mitochondrial dysfunction. *Acta Biochimica et Biophysica Sinica* 47: 730–740. <https://doi.org/10.1093/abbs/gmv061>
- Yang Y, Wang Y, Zhou Y, Deng J, Wu L (2025) Tirzepatide alleviates oxidative stress and inflammation in diabetic nephropathy via IL-17 signaling pathway. *Molecular and Cellular Biochemistry* 480: 1241–1254. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11010-024-05066-1>
- Yoon Y, Krueger EW, Oswald BJ, McNiven MA (2003) The mitochondrial protein hFis1 regulates mitochondrial fission in mammalian cells through an interaction with the dynamin-like protein DLP1. *Molecular and Cellular Biology* 23: 5409–5420. <https://doi.org/10.1128/MCB.23.15.5409-5420.2003>
- Yu T, Robotham JL, Yoon Y (2006) Increased production of reactive oxygen species in hyperglycemic conditions requires dynamic change of mitochondrial morphology. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences (USA)* 103: 2653–2658. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0511154103>
- Zafarani S, Choobineh S, Soori R (2018) The effect of 12 weeks of aerobic exercise on mitochondrial dynamics in cardiac myocytes of type 2 diabetic rats. *Sport Sciences for Health* 14: 305–312. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11332-018-0430-9>
- Zerihun M, Sukumaran S, Qvit N (2023) The Drp1-Mediated mitochondrial fission protein interactome as an emerging core player in mitochondrial dynamics and cardiovascular disease therapy. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences* 24. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms24065785>
- Zhan M, Usman IM, Sun L, Kanwar YS (2015) Disruption of renal tubular mitochondrial quality control by Myo-inositol oxygenase in diabetic kidney disease. *Journal of the American Society of Nephrology* 26: 1304–1321. <https://doi.org/10.1681/ASN.2014050457>